

The Modern Argonauts

A Multicultural Educational Programme Preparing Young People
for Contemporary Challenges
through an Innovative Use of Classical Mythology

International Conference
Faculty of “Artes Liberales”, University of Warsaw
May 22–25, 2024

The Modern Argonauts

University of Warsaw
Faculty of "Artes Liberales"
Centre for Studies on the Classical Tradition (OBTA)
and The Cluster: The Past for the Present

Conference Booklet

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for Contemporary Challenges
through an Innovative Use of Classical Mythology

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ERC Proof of Concept Grant (101122976)
within the **Our Mythical Childhood** programme

The Modern Argonauts: A Multicultural Educational Programme Preparing Young People for Contemporary Challenges through an Innovative Use of Classical Mythology. Conference Booklet
May 22–25, 2024

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and The Cluster: The Past for the Present

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Project’s Website

<https://modernargonauts.al.uw.edu.pl/>

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We wish to acknowledge also the support from the “Artes Liberales Institute” Foundation in the implementation of the Cluster activities.

For more details see: <https://modernargonauts.al.uw.edu.pl/conference>

Faculty of “Artes Liberales”

University of Warsaw

Warsaw 2024

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The Modern Argonauts

Steve K. Simons. *The Modern Argonauts: Trireme* (2023)

The international team project ***The Modern Argonauts: A Multicultural Educational Programme Preparing Young People for Contemporary Challenges through an Innovative Use of Classical Mythology*** is supported by the European Research Council's Proof of Concept Grant (October 2023–March 2025).

The ERC Proof of Concept Grants aim at maximising the value of the excellent research resulting from the preceding ERC Grants by facilitating exploration of the commercial and social innovation potential of ground breaking ideas. They are awarded on the basis of evaluation carried out by independent experts, incl. the professionals outside of the Academia.

The Modern Argonauts project has no commercial character. Our aim is to create a freely accessible, international, educational programme that prepares high schoolers for the challenges of the present day through an innovative use of Greek and Roman mythology. The programme will be available in Open Access as a handbook in game format: its users will take on the role of the “Modern Argonauts” and embark on an expedition to discover the shared mythical heritage.

We encourage the young people to lead a dialogue on important current themes via various myths: for example, via Troy on war, via Aeneas on migration, via Hephaestus on disability, via King Midas on the values, via Poseidon on marine pollution. The students also discover the masterpieces of art and learn about non-Classical mythology: for example, Maōri, Cameroonian, Hindu, and Japanese. Owing to this, they develop

a sense of community, become aware of their local and global heritage, and learn respect for different cultures.

The programme is addressed at high school students (14–19 year old), but can be used also by museums, children's universities, teacher training centres, and even families in their leisure time.

Scholars and PhD-students from the following countries take part in the preparation of the programme: Andorra, Australia, Austria, Belarus, Cameroon, Cyprus, Estonia, Germany, Greece, India, Ireland, Israel, Italy, Japan, Luxembourg, Malta, New Zealand, Poland, Slovenia, Switzerland, Ukraine, the UK, and the USA.

The Modern Argonauts builds on the potential of the *Our Mythical Childhood* programme, first of all, the preceding ERC Consolidator Grant *Our Mythical Childhood... The Reception of Classical Antiquity in Children's and Young Adults' Culture in Response to Regional and Global Challenges* (2016–2022). This programme has proved that Antiquity is a great instrument in education for three main reasons: (1) the questions that the ancients posed are still relevant, (2) myths build a cultural code that is comprehensible almost all over the world, (3) the sense of community created by myths is a source of hope for the future. The Proof of Concept ERC Grant permits us to develop these ideas and the vision of education as a joint effort of all of us – a crucial endeavour for the future of our societies worldwide. *Cras ingens iterabimus aequor...* Fair winds and following seas!

Katarzyna Marciniak

P.S. For more information in English on *The Modern Argonauts* project see:

- ▣ <https://en.uw.edu.pl/first-erc-proof-of-concept-grant-in-polish-humanities/>
- ▣ <https://erc.europa.eu/news-events/news/proof-concept-2023-highlighted-projects>
- ▣ <https://www.academia-net.org/news/katarzyna-marciniak-ancient-myths-can-encourage-high-schoolers-face-challenges-present/74218>

Website of the Project:

- ▣ <https://modernargonauts.al.uw.edu.pl/>

The University of Warsaw short video about the Project:

- ▣ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8-WtyB-Ph7U>

The Conference Programme

May 22, 2024 (Wednesday)

Ball Room, Tyszkiewicz-Potocki Palace, University of Warsaw, Krakowskie Przedmieście 32

10.00 Opening of the Conference

Introduction: **Katarzyna Marciniak**, Faculty of “Artes Liberales”, University of Warsaw

- ▣ **Robert A. Sucharski**, Dean of the Faculty of “Artes Liberales”, University of Warsaw

10.30–12.00 European Research Council (ERC) Panel

Moderator: **Jerzy Axer**, Faculty of “Artes Liberales”, University of Warsaw

- ▣ **Aneta Barkley**, European Research Council Executive Agency, Project Adviser
- ▣ **Véronique Dasen**, Faculty of Humanities, University of Fribourg, Principal Investigator of the ERC Advanced Grant “Locus Ludi” (741520)
- ▣ **Katarzyna Marciniak**, Faculty of “Artes Liberales”, University of Warsaw, Principal Investigator of the ERC Consolidator Grant “Our Mythical Childhood” (681202) and of the ERC Proof of Concept Grant “The Modern Argonauts” (101122976)
- ▣ **Anna Demner**, University of Warsaw Office for International Research and Liaison
- ▣ **Session Q&A**

12.00–12.30 Coffee break and time for the ERC-related talks and consultations

12.30–12.45 Sonya Nevin, Faculty of “Artes Liberales” UW and Panoply Vase Animation Project, and **Steve K. Simons**, Panoply Vase Animation Project, *Animating the Ancient World for the Modern Argonauts Educational Programme*

12.45–13.00 Irene Di Gioia and **Ippolita Giannotta**, Department of Classical Philology and Italian Studies, University of Bologna and Department of Philosophy, University of Göttingen, *A Mythical Quiz: How to Test the Outcome of the Lessons*

13.00–13.45 The Gods’ Playground

Moderator: **Markus Janka**, Department of Greek and Latin Philology, University of Munich

- ▣ **Julia Wollner**, Mediterranean Magazine “Lente”, *Meet Atlas*
- ▣ **Katarzyna Marciniak**, Faculty of “Artes Liberales” UW, *Meet Prometheus*
- ▣ **Lisa Maurice** and **Ayelet Peer**, Department of Classical Studies, Bar-Ilan University, *Meet Deucalion and Pyrrha*

14.00 Lunch for Speakers and time for the ERC-related talks and consultations

15.30–17.00 Women's Mythical Agency

Moderator: **Lisa Maurice**, Department of Classical Studies, Bar-Ilan University

▣ **Katarzyna Jerzak**, Krieger School of Arts and Sciences, Johns Hopkins University, *Meet Eros and Psyche*

▣ **Oksana Ruchynska**, Department of Ancient and Medieval History, V.N. Karazin Kharkiv National University and Faculty of Humanities, University of Fribourg, and **Alfred Twardecki**, Faculty of "Artes Liberales" UW and Institute for History of Material Culture, Polish Academy of Sciences, *Meet the Amazons*

▣ **Véronique Dasen**, Faculty of Humanities, University of Fribourg, and **Sonya Nevin**, Faculty of "Artes Liberales" UW and Panoply Vase Animation Project, *Meet Atalanta*

▣ **Véronique Dasen**, Faculty of Humanities, University of Fribourg, and **Krzysztof Korwin-Piotrowski**, Faculty of "Artes Liberales" UW and ORFEO Foundation, *Meet Kallisto*

▣ **Katarzyna Marciniak**, Faculty of "Artes Liberales" UW, *Meet the Sirens*

17.00–17.15 Coffee break

17.15–18.45 Beyond Colchis

Moderator: **Katarzyna Jerzak**, Krieger School of Arts and Sciences, Johns Hopkins University

▣ **David Movrin**, Department of Classics, University of Ljubljana, *Meet the Dragons*

▣ **Tajinder Kaur**, Department of Anthropology, University of Delhi, and **Sonya Nevin**, Faculty of "Artes Liberales" UW and Panoply Vase Animation Project, *Meet Indrani and Iris*

▣ **Ariko Kato**, School of World Liberal Arts, Nagoya University of Foreign Studies, *Meet Kamuy*

▣ **Eleanor A. Dasi**, **Divine Che Neba**, and **Daniel A. Nkemleke**, Ecole Normale Supérieure, University of Yaoundé I, *Learn of the Origin of the Dry and Rainy Seasons*

▣ **Mai Musié**, Swansea University and University of Oxford, *Meet Perseus and Andromeda*

19.00 Dinner for Speakers and time for the ERC-related talks and consultations

May 23, 2024 (Thursday)

Columned Hall, Faculty of History Building, University of Warsaw, Krakowskie Przedmieście 26/28

9.30 Maria Wiśniewska, Faculty of "Artes Liberales" UW, *Learning Leadership through Mythology*

9.45–10.30 Schools Session: Reports on the Lessons Testing

- ▣ **Barbara Strycharczyk's Class**, "Strumienie" High School in Józefów
- ▣ **Anna Wojciechowska's Class**, Mikołaj Rej XI High School in Warsaw

10.30–11.00 Faculty of "Artes Liberales" Students' Presentations, *Mythology Just Around the Corner***11.00–11.30 Coffee break****11.30–12.15 Prolegomena**

Moderator: **Elżbieta Olechowska**, Faculty of "Artes Liberales" UW

- ▣ **Helen Lovatt**, Department of Classics, University of Nottingham, *The Myth of the Argonauts*
- ▣ **Marta Pszczolińska**, Faculty of "Artes Liberales" UW, *Know Your Name*
- ▣ **Katarzyna Marciniak**, Faculty of "Artes Liberales" UW, *Our Mythical Template*

12.15–13.00 The Future Routes of the Modern Argonauts

Moderator: **Oksana Ruchynska**, Department of Ancient and Medieval History, V.N. Karazin Kharkiv National University and Faculty of Humanities, University of Fribourg

- ▣ **Kerttu Männiste**, Kadriorg Art Museum in Tallinn, Art Museum of Estonia, *The Modern Argonauts Programme and Ovid at the Kadriorg Art Museum 2025 Exhibition*
- ▣ **Davide Iengo**, Faculty of Humanities, University of Pisa and Faculty of "Artes Liberales" UW (Student Mobility Erasmus Traineeship), *The Italian Translation of a Choice of the Modern Argonauts Lessons*
- ▣ **Viktoriia Kotenko**, Institute of Archaeology, Ukrainian National Academy of Sciences, *A Report on Testing the Demeter and Persephone Lesson in the Lyceum No. 6 "Leader" of the Poltava City Council, Poltava, Ukraine*

13.00–13.15 Coffee break**13.15–14.00 Troy Story**

Moderator: **David Movrin**, Department of Classics, University of Ljubljana

- ▣ **Julia Wollner**, Mediterranean Magazine "Lente", *Meet Laocoon*
- ▣ **Julia Wollner**, Mediterranean Magazine "Lente", *Meet Aeneas and Dido*
- ▣ **Sonja Schreiner**, Department of Classical Philology, Medieval and Neolatin Studies, University of Vienna, *Meet Achilles*

14.00 Lunch for Speakers**15.30–16.30 Navigare necesse est**

Moderator: **Bridget Martin**, School of Classics, University College Dublin

▣ **Irene Di Gioia**, Department of Classical Philology and Italian Studies, University of Bologna and Department of Philosophy, University of Göttingen, *Meet Poseidon*

▣ **Sonya Nevin**, Faculty of “Artes Liberales” UW and Panoply Vase Animation Project, *Meet Odysseus and Penelope*

▣ **Katarzyna Marciniak**, Faculty of “Artes Liberales” UW, *Meet Cadmus and Europe*

16.30–17.30 A Mythical Tale of Crete

Moderator: **Krishni Burns**, College of Liberal Arts and Sciences, University of Illinois Chicago

▣ **Bettina Kümmerling-Meibauer**, Faculty of Humanities, University of Tübingen, *Meet Daedalus and Icarus*

▣ **Katarzyna Jerzak**, Krieger School of Arts and Sciences, Johns Hopkins University, *Meet Talos*

▣ **Krzysztof Rybak**, Faculty of “Artes Liberales” UW, *Meet Theseus and the Minotaur*

17.30–18.00 Coffee Break

18.00–19.00 Katabasis (and Back)

Moderator: **Bettina Kümmerling-Meibauer**, Faculty of Humanities, University of Tübingen

▣ **Bridget Martin**, School of Classics, University College Dublin, *Meet Hades*

▣ **Marta Pszczolińska** and **Maria Wiśniewska**, Faculty of “Artes Liberales” UW, *Meet Demeter and Persephone*

▣ **Alfred Twardecki**, Faculty of “Artes Liberales” UW and Institute for History of Material Culture, Polish Academy of Sciences, and **Krzysztof Korwin-Piotrowski**, Faculty of “Artes Liberales” UW and ORFEO Foundation, *Meet Orpheus and Eurydice*

▣ **Krzysztof Korwin-Piotrowski**, Faculty of “Artes Liberales” UW and ORFEO Foundation, *See Arcadia*

19.30 Dinner for Speakers

May 24, 2024 (Friday)

Conference Room, Collegium Artes Liberales (CLAS), Faculty of “Artes Liberales” UW, White Villa, Dobra 72

9.30–11.00 On Olympus

Moderator: **Caroline Bristow**, Cambridge School Classics Project, University of Cambridge

▣ **Owen Hodkinson**, Department of Classics, University of Leeds, *Meet Zeus and Hera*

▣ **Marta Pszczolińska**, Faculty of “Artes Liberales” UW, *Meet Apollo*

- ▣ **Marta Pszczolińska**, Faculty of “Artes Liberales” UW, *Meet Hephaestus*
- ▣ **Sonya Nevin**, Faculty of “Artes Liberales” UW and Panoply Vase Animation Project, *Meet Ares*
- ▣ **Elżbieta Olechowska**, Faculty of “Artes Liberales” UW, *Meet Dionysus*
- ▣ **Katarzyna Marciniak**, Faculty of “Artes Liberales” UW, *Meet Hermes*

11.00–11.30 Coffee Break

11.30–13.00 The Divine Might of the Goddesses

Moderator: **Susan Deacy**, Department of Classics and Ancient History, University of Bristol

- ▣ **Amy Smith**, Department of Classics and Ure Museum of Greek Archaeology, University of Reading, and **Katerina Volioti**, Department of Humanities, University of Roehampton London, *Meet Aphrodite*
- ▣ **Krishni Burns**, College of Liberal Arts and Sciences, University of Illinois Chicago, and **Nava Cohen**, Department of Classics, Northwestern University, *Meet Hestia*
- ▣ **Krishni Burns**, College of Liberal Arts and Sciences, University of Illinois Chicago, and **Nava Cohen**, Department of Classics, Northwestern University, *Meet Athena*
- ▣ **Julia Wollner**, Mediterranean Magazine “Lente”, *Meet Artemis*
- ▣ **Caroline Bristow**, Cambridge School Classics Project, University of Cambridge, and *experta loci* **Kerttu Männiste**, Kadriorg Art Museum in Tallinn, Art Museum of Estonia, *Meet Actaeon*

13.00 Lunch for Speakers

14.00–15.30 The New Faces of Heroism

Moderator: **Amy Smith**, Department of Classics and Ure Museum of Greek Archaeology, University of Reading

- ▣ **Małgorzata Borowska** and **Przemysław Kordos**, Faculty of “Artes Liberales” UW, *Meet Chiron*
- ▣ **Valentina Garulli**, Department of Classical Philology and Italian Studies, University of Bologna, *Meet Asclepius*
- ▣ **Susan Deacy**, Department of Classics and Ancient History, University of Bristol, *Choose with Hercules*
- ▣ **Effrosyni Kostara**, Department of Education, Frederick University, *Meet Herakles (Labours)*
- ▣ **Hanna Paulouskaya**, Faculty of “Artes Liberales” UW, *Meet Bellerophon and Pegasus*

15.30–15.45 Coffee Break

15.45–17.00 The Choices

Moderator: **Divine Che Neba**, Ecole Normale Supérieure, University of Yaoundé I

▣ **Raimund Fichtel**, Department of Greek and Latin Philology, University of Munich, **Berkan Sariaydin**, Department of Greek and Latin Philology, University of Munich, and **Maria Wiśniewska**, Faculty of “Artes Liberales” UW, *Meet King Midas*

▣ **Frances Foster**, Faculty of Education, University of Cambridge, *Archaeology and Mythology: Animating a Composite Midas*

▣ **Marta Pszczolińska**, Faculty of “Artes Liberales” UW, *Meet the Sphinx*

▣ **Arlene Holmes-Henderson**, Department of Classics and Ancient History, Durham University, and *experta loci* **Alexandra Saz Peñamaria**, Interdisciplinary Research Group on Education, University of Andorra, *Meet Narcissus and Echo*

17.30 Dinner for Speakers

19.30 Concert in the Warsaw Philharmonic for Speakers

May 25, 2024 (Saturday)

Conference Room, Centre for Studies on the Classical Tradition (OBTA), Faculty of “Artes Liberales” UW, Zamoyski Palace, Nowy Świat 69

9.30–10.30 The Song Weavers

Moderator: **Ariko Kato**, School of World Liberal Arts, Nagoya University of Foreign Studies

▣ **Babette Puetz**, School of Languages and Cultures, Victoria University of Wellington – Te Herenga Waka, *Meet the Pleiades*

▣ **Marta Pszczolińska**, Faculty of “Artes Liberales” UW, *Meet Calypso*

▣ **Hanna Paulouskaya**, Faculty of “Artes Liberales” UW, *Meet Electra*

▣ **Maria Pia Napolitano de Majo**, Department of Greek and Latin Philology, University of Munich, and *expertus loci* **Jean Krier**, Musée National d’Archéologie, d’Histoire et d’Art (MNAHA), Luxembourg, *Meet the Muses*

10.30–11.30 The Identity Quests

Moderator: **Sonya Nevin**, Faculty of “Artes Liberales” UW and Panoply Vase Animation Project

▣ **Elizabeth Hale**, School of Humanities, Arts and Social Sciences, University of New England, *Meet Circe*

▣ **Pietro Rosa**, Department of Classical Philology and Italian Studies, University of Bologna and Liceo Classico Statale Marco Minghetti, Bologna, and **Renzo Tosi**, Department of Classical Philology and Italian Studies, University of Bologna, *Meet Medea*

▣ **Markus Janka**, Department of Greek and Latin Philology, University of Munich, and **Michael Stierstorfer**, Gymnasium Kloster Schäftlarn, *Meet Medusa*

11.30–12.00 Coffee Break

12.00–12.30 To the Edge of the World

Moderator: **Effrosyni Kostara**, Department of Education, Frederick University

▣ **Elżbieta Olechowska**, Faculty of “Artes Liberales” UW, and *expertus loci* **Adrian-Mario Gellel**, Faculty of Education, University of Malta, *See Atlantis*

▣ **Rachel Bryant Davies**, School of Languages, Linguistics and Film, Queen Mary University of London, *See the Isles of the Blessed*

12.30 Summary of the Conference, incl. the discussion on the next stages of the work on the Handbook

Moderator: **Katarzyna Marciniak**, Faculty of “Artes Liberales” UW

13.00 Lunch for Speakers

16.00–19.00 Guided Visit to the Royal Łazienki Museum – mythology in the public space and the potential of *The Modern Argonauts Handbook* in museum lessons and workshops

20.00 Farewell dinner for Speakers

For more see: <https://modernargonauts.al.uw.edu.pl/>

This Project has received funding from the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union’s Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 101122976, *The Modern Argonauts: A Multicultural Educational Programme Preparing Young People for Contemporary Challenges through an Innovative Use of Classical Mythology*, ERC Proof of Concept Grant (2023–2025).

For the conference materials see:

<https://modernargonauts.al.uw.edu.pl/conference>

For the Zoom link please write to Olga Strycharczyk:

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Cover images by Matylda Tracewska and Steve K. Simons.

Our Mythical Crew

People and Their Myths (in alphabetical order)

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A Myth of Changing Seasons

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The Isles of the Blessed

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Hercules (Choice)

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Poseidon and Our Mythical Quiz

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King Midas in Animation (The Cluster Lecture)

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Our Mythical Quiz

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Daedalus and Icarus

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The Myth of the Argonauts

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Experta loci (Estonia) and presentation of the 2025 Ovid exhibition at Kadriorg Art Museum

Katarzyna Marciniak

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Cadmus and Europa, Hermes, Prometheus, and The Sirens

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A Myth of Changing Seasons

Sonya Nevin

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Atalanta, Ares, Iris, A Myth of Changing Seasons, and Odysseus and Penelope

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A Myth of Changing Seasons

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Artemis, Atlas, Dido and Aeneas, and Laocoon

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A very special mention of gratitude

- ▣ for **Prof. Sheila Murnaghan** (Department of Classical Studies, University of Pennsylvania) and **Prof. Deborah H. Roberts** (Department of Classics, Haverford College) who have always believed deep enough and strong enough in the Our Mythical Childhood idea, even in the moment of its very beginning,

- ▣ for **Prof. Giovanna Alvoni** (Department of Classical Philology and Italian Studies, University of Bologna), **Prof. Edith Hall** (Department of Classics and Ancient History, Durham University), **Prof. Wilfried Stroh** (Department of Greek and Latin Philology, University of Munich), and **Prof. Karoline Thaidigsmann** (Institute of Slavic Studies, University of Heidelberg) who have always offered their support to the OMC programme,

- ▣ for **Ms Maria Makarewicz** (Faculty of “Artes Liberales”, University of Warsaw) for her outstanding support in the implementation of the ERC Consolidator Grant,

- ▣ for **Mirosław Kaźmierczak** – director and photographer, UW Press Office collaborator, for his kind patience and care of our mythical visual documentation,

- ▣ and for **Mr Zbigniew Karaszewski** – a renowned artist, graduate from the Academy of Fine Arts in Warsaw – and **Mr Janusz Olech** – a master of the art of layout, for their illuminating designs for our mythical materials, including this conference booklet, and for their excellent cooperation on the series “Our Mythical Childhood” at the University of Warsaw Press.

European Research Council (ERC)

European Research Council
Established by the European Commission

The **European Research Council (ERC)**, set up by the European Union in 2007, is the premier European funding organization for excellent frontier research. Its mission is to encourage the highest quality research in Europe through competitive funding and to support investigator-driven frontier research across all fields, based on scientific excellence. The ERC offers four core grant schemes: Starting Grants, Consolidator Grants, Advanced Grants, and Synergy Grants. The fifth scheme is built by the Proof of Concept Grants. They aim at maximising the value of the excellent research that the ERC funds, by supporting further work (i.e., activities which were not scheduled to be funded by the original, core ERC frontier research grant) to verify the innovation potential of ideas arising from ERC funded projects. The PoC Grants' objective is to enable ERC-funded ideas to progress on the path from ground-breaking research towards innovation.

Research funded by the ERC is expected to lead to advances at the frontiers of knowledge and to set a clear and inspirational target for frontier research across Europe. Excellence is the sole criterion on the basis of which ERC frontier research grants are awarded. The ERC funds creative researchers of any nationality and age, and supports the idea of citizen science and Open Access to research results.*

During *The Modern Argonauts* conference a special event is planned – **an ERC session dedicated to the ERC Grants** for the potential candidates with the participation by **Dr Aneta Barkley**, Project Adviser from the European Research Council Executive Agency in Brussels. Her presentation and expertise will help the scholars considering an application to understand the idea and the implementation of the ERC Grants.

* The above text about the ERC has been extracted from the materials available at <https://erc.europa.eu>.

The Our Mythical Childhood Research Programme

The Our Mythical Childhood Programme was established in 2011 at the Institute for Interdisciplinary Studies “Artes Liberales” (now: Faculty of “Artes Liberales”), University of Warsaw. It regards the reception of Classical Antiquity in children’s and young adults’ culture. We consider the intersection between these two fields to be a vital space where the development of human identity takes place, both in previous epochs and in our times. Indeed, each of us has gone through the experience of childhood and many people have had contacts with Classical Antiquity as a cultural experience – transmitted as it is all over the globe and across the ages via education, through myriad of interpersonal contacts, and today owing to the charm of global popular culture. Hence, the ancient tradition has built a familiar code of communication understandable in local and global contexts alike. A major methodological innovation of the Our Mythical Childhood research, developed in the milieu of OBTA – Centre for Studies on the Classical Tradition (now a permanent unit of the Faculty of “Artes Liberales”), founded in 1991 by Prof. Jerzy Axer (https://www.al.uw.edu.pl/antiquity_and_we) – consists in the application of regional perspectives without the pejorative implication of regional as inferior. On the contrary, we recognize it as extremely valuable, for in this sense, Classical Reception Studies serve as a mirror of transformations around the globe (www.omc.obta.al.uw.edu.pl).

Matylda Tracevska, *Our Mythical Childhood* (2013)

The OMC Programme comprises (so far!) the following stages:

2012–2013 *Our Mythical Childhood... The Classics and Children's Literature between East and West*, Loeb Classical Library Foundation Grant,

Unterstützt von / Supported by

Alexander von Humboldt
Stiftung / Foundation

2014–2017 *Chasing Mythical Beasts... The Reception of Creatures from Graeco-Roman Mythology in Children's and Young Adults' Culture as a Transformation Marker*, Alexander von Humboldt Foundation Alumni Award for Innovative Networking Initiatives,

2016–2022 *Our Mythical Childhood... The Reception of Classical Antiquity in Children's and Young Adults' Culture in Response to Regional and Global Challenges*, ERC Consolidator Grant, 681202, carried

out in partnership with Bar-Ilan University, University of New England, University of Roehampton, and University of Yaoundé I, along with experts also from all around the globe,

2023–2025 *The Modern Argonauts: A Multicultural Educational Programme Preparing Young People for Contemporary Challenges through an Innovative Use of Classical Mythology*, ERC Proof of Concept Grant, 101122976, see above, p. 7.

I also wish to acknowledge the support from the “*Artes Liberales* Institute” Foundation in the development of the OMC Programme.

We believe deeply in citizen science and a broad collaboration with scholars as well as other members of the society. Thus, the dissemination aspect is very important to us. We lead several social media profiles and four scholarly blogs. Our aim is to contribute to establishing **a new holistic model for work in the Humanities** in international cooperation – a model on the frontiers of research, education, and culture: **Our Mythical Community**.

Katarzyna Marciniak

The Cluster: The Past for the Present

The Cluster: The Past for the Present – International Research and Educational Programme is a joint endeavour of the Faculty of “Artes Liberales” of the University of Warsaw, Dipartimento di Storia Culture Civiltà and Dipartimento di Filologia Classica e Italianistica of the Università di Bologna, Fakultät für Sprach- und Literaturwissenschaften of the Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität München, the Faculty of Education of the University of Cambridge, and the Faculté des lettres et des sciences humaines of the Université de Fribourg.

Our aim is to make the full use of the potential of our years-long collaboration in the field of Reception Studies, *inter alia*, within the Harvard University Loeb Classical Library Foundation (2012–2013), Alexander von Humboldt Foundation Alumni Award for Innovative Networking Initiatives (2014–2017), and the European Research Council Consolidator Grant (2016–2022) for the project *Our Mythical Childhood... The Reception of Classical Antiquity in Children's and Young Adults' Culture in Response to Regional and Global Challenges*, and the ERC Proof of Concept Grant *The Modern Argonauts: A Multicultural Educational Programme Preparing Young People for Contemporary Challenges through an Innovative Use of Classical Mythology* (2023–2025). We focus in particular on:

- ▣ Developing academic projects for the benefit of society (“citizen science”), with a particular focus on the education of the youth – from kindergarten to high school;
- ▣ Disseminating and applying research results in cultural and artistic activities, also in cooperation with non-academic partners and institutions;
- ▣ Organizing workshops and projects involving students, early-stage researchers, and teachers.

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The major activities of the Cluster since its establishment in May 2017:

October 2017 Munich: the international conference for teachers and educators *Verjüngte Antike trifft The Past for the Present: Griechisch-römische Mythologie und Historie in Kinder- und Jugendmedien der Gegenwartskultur*;

December 2017 Warsaw: the international seminar on *The Reception of the Myth of Sisyphus*;

May 2018 Warsaw: the international workshops *The Present Meets the Past*, in the European Year of Cultural Heritage;

June 2018 Bologna: the international conference *Figure dell'altro. Identità, alterità, stranierità*;

October 2018 Munich: the international conference for teachers and educators *Digitale Bildung – zwischen Hype und Hybris*;

December 2018 Warsaw: the seminar on *The Reception of Caesar in Children's and Young Adults' Culture* and the concert *Many Languages of Music* by Rafał Janiak from the Fryderyk Chopin University of Music;

February–March 2019 Warsaw and Bologna: Homer Reading Sessions within the Festival Européen Latin Grec;

October 2019 Munich: international conference *Mutatas dicere formas: Verjüngung der Antike durch Übersetzungen und Adaptionen im Kontakt der Kulturen*;

December 2019 Warsaw: Ciceronian Congress *Cicero, Society, and the Idea of Artes Liberales*, with the Société Internationale des Amis de Cicéron, OBTA, and CLAS: <http://www.obta.al.uw.edu.pl/en/cicero-congress>;

February 2020 Cambridge: international conference *Mythology and Education: History and Practice*;

July and October 2020 Munich: international online workshops and conference *HISTORMYTHOS: Intermediale, interkulturelle und diachrone Perspektiven der Antikenrezeption*;

November 2020 Vienna: international online conference *Child-friendly “Explorations of the Myth”: Modern Reception Strategies from Adaptation to Transformation* by Sonja Schreiner and Austrian Society for the Research into Children’s and Young Adult Literature;

December 2020 Bologna: Giovanna Alvonì, Stefano Colangelo, Roberto Batisti, eds., *Figure dell’altro. Identità, alterità, stranierità, Eikasmós: Quaderni Bolognesi di Filologia Classica. Studi Online 3*, Bologna: Pàtron Editore, 2020, 481 pp. – book publication of the 2018 conference proceedings *Figure dell’altro. Identità, alterità, stranierità*;

May 2021 Warsaw–London: The first ACCLAIM Network online event to discuss autism and mythology in children’s education, organized by Susan Deacy;

ACCLAIM: **Autism Connecting** with CLAssically-Inspired **Mythology Network**

The first ACCLAIM Network online event

October 2021 Munich: Michael Stierstorfer, ed., *Extrablatt Antike Aktuell 2021*, Deutsche Akademie für Kinder- und Jugendliteratur;

March 2022 Bologna: Sophocles Reading Sessions within the Festival Européen Latin Grec;

June 2022 Warsaw: The International Students' and PhD Students' Conference *Antiquity Today: Fascinating, Relevant, Beneficial*, online, <http://www.omc.obta.al.uw.edu.pl/antiquity-today>;

Phot. Maria Makarewicz

March 2023 Bologna: Virgil Reading Sessions within the Festival Européen Latin Grec;

Lettura pubblica dell'Eneide di Virgilio

A cura degli studenti del Liceo Galvani e del Liceo Minghetti di Bologna

Festival Européen Latin Grec

Venerdì 24 marzo 2023
ore 15:30

Link all'evento
Contatti: valentina.gerullitombia.it

Incontri di preparazione e approfondimento on line			
17/01/2023	24/01/2023	13/02/2023	21/02/2023
Geografia dell'Eneide	Le giornate di un traduttore: appunti da un viaggio nell'Eneide	Epica e tragedia nell'Eneide	La giunta di Isole (da Catullo a Boris Johnson)
ore 15:30 (link)	ore 15:30 (link)	ore 15:30 (link)	ore 15:30 (link)
Prof. A. Santoro (Univ. di Siena)	Prof. A. Pi (Univ. di Siena)	Bibliotecaria Pasolini Liceo Galvani Prof. A. Cusi (Univ. di Bologna)	Auditorium Liceo Minghetti Prof. G. Peri (Univ. di Bologna)
L'Eneide di Virgilio: nuove prospettive di interpretazione intertestuale e intermediale			
ore 15:30 (link)			
Bibliotecaria Pasolini Liceo Galvani Prof. M. Janku (Univ. di Monaco)			

October 2023 Warsaw: The International Students' and PhD Students' Conference *Antiquity Today II: Inspiring, Inclusive, Universal*, online, <http://www.omc.obta.al.uw.edu.pl/antiquity-today-2>;

Phot. Maria Makarewicz

March 2024 Bologna: Aristophanes Reading Sessions within the Festival Européen Latin Grec;

Lettura pubblica: Le donne al Parlamento di Aristofane

A cura degli studenti del Liceo Galvani e del Liceo Minghetti di Bologna

Festival Européen Latin Grec

Venerdì 15 marzo 2024
ore 18:00

Auditorium Istit. Biagi, Biblioteca Solinaschi, Piazza Natuno 3, Bologna

Contatti: fidi.letturapubblica@unibo.it

Incontri di preparazione e approfondimento in presenza e on line			
22/01/2024	03/02/2024	26/02/2024	13/03/2024
Compiete all'ekfrasia: dal golpe all'utopia	La vittoria delle donne: come e perché. E durerà?	Scene finali nelle Ecclesiazuse di Aristofane	Le <i>Ginose al Parlamento</i> di Aristofane: <i>mundus inversus</i> paradisiaco o utopia politico-sociale?
ore 14:30 (link)	ore 14:30 (link)	ore 14:30 (link)	ore 14:30 (link)
Biblioteca Pasolini Liceo Galvani Prof. V. Tommaseo (Univ. di Bologna)	Biblioteca Pasolini Liceo Galvani Prof. A. Capra (Univ. di Milano)	Auditorium Liceo Minghetti Prof. P. Talaro (Univ. di Bari)	Auditorium Liceo Minghetti Prof. M. Janku (Univ. di Monaco)

April 2024 Vienna: Katarzyna Marciniak and Sonja Schreiner's presentation of *The Modern Argonauts* in the journal *Circulare*;

Ein Bericht von der Reise der modernen Argonaut:innen

oder ein internationales Bildungsprogramm auf der Grundlage der klassischen Mythologie, das Jugendliche zum Dialog über aktuelle Themen ermuntert

April 2024 Warsaw: Jan Parandowski Day

Autumn 2024 Munich: Markus Janka, Raimund Fichtel, and Berkan Sariaydin, eds., *Mythen Multimedial: Modernste Antike in der Gegenwartskultur* (forthcoming).

A short presentation of the workshops *The Present Meets the Past* within the Cluster and the ERC Consolidator Grant *Our Mythical Childhood* (European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme, grant agreement No 681202) in May 2018 at the Faculty of "Artes Liberales", can be watched at: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2RizUWYMW0Q>. A reportage about the Cluster can be watched at: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HfypV5PUMUc> (YouTube channel *Our Mythical Childhood*).

We wish to acknowledge the support from the "Artes Liberales Institute" Foundation in the organization of the Cluster's development. More endeavours coming soon!

The Our Mythical Childhood Book Series

Katarzyna Marciniak, ed., *Our Mythical Childhood... The Classics and Literature for Children and Young Adults*, in the series “Metaforms. Studies in the Reception of Classical Antiquity” 8, Leiden and Boston: Brill, 2016, 526 pp.

Open Access:

<https://brill.com/view/title/32883>

Katarzyna Marciniak, ed., *Chasing Mythical Beasts: The Reception of Ancient Monsters in Children's and Young Adults' Culture*, in the series “Studies in European Children's and Young Adult Literature” 8, Heidelberg: Universitätsverlag Winter, 2020, 623 pp.

Open Access:

https://www.winter-verlag.de/en/detail/978-3-8253-6995-8/Marciniak_Ed_Chasing_Mythical_Beasts/

Lisa Maurice, ed., *Our Mythical Education: The Reception of Classical Myth Worldwide in Formal Education, 1900-2020*, in the series “Our Mythical Childhood”, Warsaw: Warsaw University Press, 580 pp.

Open Access:

<https://www.wuw.pl/product-eng-14887-Our-Mythical-Education-The-Reception-of-Classical-Myth-Worldwide-in-Formal-Education-1900-2020-PDF.html>

Elizabeth Hale and Miriam Riverlea, *Classical Mythology and Children's Literature: An Alphabetical Odyssey*, in the series "Our Mythical Childhood", Warsaw: University of Warsaw Press, 2021, 202 pp.

Open Access:

<https://www.wuw.pl/product-pol-17978-Classical-Mythology-and-Childrens-Literature-An-Alphabetical-Odyssey-PDF.html>

Katarzyna Marciniak, ed., *Our Mythical Hope: The Ancient Myths as Medicine for the Hardships of Life in Children's and Young Adults' Culture*, in the series "Our Mythical Childhood", Warsaw: University of Warsaw Press, 2021, 835 pp.

Open Access:

<https://www.wuw.pl/product-pol-16830-Our-Mythical-Hope-The-Ancient-Myths-as-Medicine-for-the-Hardships-of-Life-in-Childrens-and-Young-Adults-Culture-PDF.html>

Susan Deacy, *What Would Hercules Do? Lessons for Autistic Children Using Classical Myth*, in the series "Our Mythical Childhood", Warsaw: University of Warsaw Press, 2023, 202 pp.

Open Access:

<https://www.wuw.pl/product-pol-18699-What-Would-Hercules-Do-Lessons-for-Autistic-Children-Using-Classical-Myth-PDF.html>

Sonya Nevin, ed., *Teaching Ancient Greece: Lesson Plans, Vase Animations, and Resources*, in the series "Our Mythical Childhood", Warsaw: University of Warsaw Press, 2024, 344 pp.

Open Access coming soon! Please check on the Publisher's website:

<https://www.wuw.pl/tra-pol-58207-Our-Mythical-Childhood.html>

Elżbieta Olechowska, *This Is the Song That Never Ends: Classical Mythology in the Twenty-First-Century Audiovisual Series for Young Adults*, in the series “Our Mythical Childhood”, Warsaw: University of Warsaw Press, 2024, forthcoming.

Katarzyna Marciniak, ed., *Our Mythical History: Children's and Young Adults' Culture in Response to the Heritage of Ancient Greece and Rome*, in the series “Our Mythical Childhood”, Warsaw: University of Warsaw Press, 2024, forthcoming.

Katarzyna Marciniak, ed., *Our Mythical Nature: The Classics and Environmental Issues in Children's and Young Adults' Culture*, in the series “Our Mythical Childhood”, Warsaw: University of Warsaw Press, 2024, forthcoming.

More publications coming soon!

Our Mythical Patrons

We are most grateful to the international institutions involved in the study and popularisation of Classical Antiquity worldwide for their readiness to help disseminate the results of *The Modern Argonauts* project. Gratias Vobis agimus maximas!

Fédération Internationale des Associations d'Études Classiques
<https://www.fiecnet.org/>

We invite you to follow the 75 Years of FIEC series of lectures:

<https://www.fiecnet.org/75-years-fiec>

Advocating Classics Education

Advocating Classics Education, UK

<https://aceclassics.org.uk/>

Associazione Italiana di Cultura Classica

<https://www.aicc-nazionale.com/>

Cambridge School Classics Project

<https://www.cambridgescp.com/>

ERC Advanced Grant *Locus Ludi: The Cultural Fabric of Play and Games in Classical Antiquity* (741520), PI Prof. Véronique Dasen, University of Fribourg

<https://locusludi.ch/>

Société Internationale des Amis de Cicéron

<https://tulliana.eu/en/project/>

Ure Museum of Greek Archaeology, University of Reading

<https://collections.reading.ac.uk/ure-museum/>

Our Mythical Schools

Throughout the whole Our Mythical Childhood programme, our guiding principle is the idea of contributing to a new, holistic model for work in the Humanities on the frontiers of research, education, and culture. Thus, we work closely with teachers in order to engage the young people in their first scholarly attempts. Among our results in this matter, we wish to mention school sessions, conference presentations, reportages, theatre performances, and – last but not least – the first books prepared by the high schoolers within various stages of the programme (see the series “OBTA Studies in Classical Reception: Schools Endeavour Educational Materials”). For more see: <http://omc.obta.al.uw.edu.pl/community>.

We are most pleased to continue our collaboration with the members of the school milieu also in *The Modern Argonauts* project. This is a matter of crucial importance, as each lesson is tested in the real school environment by teachers and students. Their precious feedback helps us prepare the final versions of the lessons in the hope that Our Mythical Handbook will serve readers well. At the moment the following schools take part in our mythical endeavour:

- ▣ “Strumienie” High School, Józefów, Poland
- ▣ Bundesgymnasium Wien 13, Fichtnergasse, Vienna, Austria
- ▣ Faith Comprehensive High School Obili, Yaoundé, Cameroon
- ▣ Flint Hill School, Oakton, VA, USA
- ▣ Franky Comprehensive Secondary School, Melen-Yaoundé, Cameroon
- ▣ Gymnasium Schäftlarn, Kloster Schäftlarn, Bayern, Germany
- ▣ I Bartłomiej Nowodworski High School, Kraków, Poland

- ▣ Jean Monnet Private High School, Warsaw, Poland
- ▣ Kharkiv Lyceum No 11 Danylo Didik of the Kharkiv City Council, Kharkiv, Ukraine
- ▣ Latin School of Chicago, Chicago, IL, USA
- ▣ Liceo Ginnasio Luigi Galvani, Bologna, Italy
- ▣ Liceo Ginnasio Statale Marco Minghetti, Bologna, Italy
- ▣ Liceo Vincenzo Gioberti, Turin, Italy
- ▣ Lyceum No. 6 “Leader” of the Poltava City Council, Poltava, Ukraine
- ▣ Mada International College, Yaoundé, Cameroon
- ▣ Peace Home Comprehensive Evening School Etoug-Ebe, Yaoundé, Cameroon
- ▣ Samuel Marsden Collegiate School, Marsden Avenue, Karori, Wellington 6012, Private Bag 17000, New Zealand
- ▣ St. Olave’s Grammar School, Orpington, Kent, UK
- ▣ Władysław Hasiór State Secondary School of Fine Arts, Koszalin, Poland
- ▣ X Bolesław Chrobry School Complex for Motor Vehicles, Koszalin, Poland
- ▣ XI Mikołaj Rej High School, Warsaw, Poland

During the conference in May 2024 the teachers and high schoolers from the following schools will present the results of the lesson tests:

“Strumienie” High School in Józefów

the group guided by Barbara Strycharczyk, teacher of Latin and Ancient Culture

Mikołaj Rej XI High School in Warsaw

the group guided by Anna Wojciechowska, teacher of Latin and Ancient Culture

Our journey continues and we invite warmly high schools to participate in *The Modern Argonauts* project and test our mythical lessons! For details see here: https://al.uw.edu.pl/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/Modern_Argonauts_schools_invitation_1.12.2023.pdf

Thanking the school headmasters, the teachers, the students and their parents or tutors for their engagement, let us quote Rej High School's motto, originating from the *Thebaid* of Statius: “Cheer up! / Have courage!” – in Latin: **Macte animo!**

Mythology Just Around the Corner: A Students' Project

The Faculty of “Artes Liberales” is a unique place, where the scholars and students can cooperate within research projects, thus building a Community. We have been practicing this approach within the Our Mythical Childhood Seminar since the very beginning of the OMC Programme. For example, in the academic year 2012/2013, within the project *Our Mythical Childhood... The Classics and Children's Literature Between East & West*, we prepared jointly a **catalogue** of references to Classical Antiquity in Polish children's and young adult literature (Open Access: www.al.uw.edu.pl/omc_catalogue).

During the next years, the students participated in our mythical conferences, gave presentations, worked on their first scholarly papers, etc. In March 2020 we started publishing various educational and popularizing materials to try to answer, at least to a small extent, the needs manifesting themselves in the situation of the pandemic that limited the mobility and placed new challenges in front of education. Believing that Classical Antiquity might teach us, move, and entertain – in accordance with the ancient maxim *docere, movere, delectare* – we named this initiative **Find the Force!**, in the hope of supporting the efforts of the educators and of the parents and tutors searching for ideas on how to spend time together across the generations and in a creative way, with the Classics

as a source of uplifting power (<http://omc.obta.al.uw.edu.pl/find-the-force>). It was within this initiative that the students entered also on the artistic ground, for example, by translating poems by Louise Glück and Margaret Atwood.

Zbigniew Karaszewski. *Find the Force!* (2020)

Last year, we made a step further. We studied theory of picture books and we read several examples of this genre with a focus on the classical content. Next, the students prepared their own picture books. What did Apollo learn as a pre-schooler? What does a day in the life of Cerberus look like? Where did the mythical creatures go? Who did little Pygmalion want to become and did he fulfil his dream? What does Artemis do today? These were the questions faced by the participants in the 2022/23 Our Mythical Childhood Seminar. You can see the results (in Polish) here: <http://www.omc.obta.al.uw.edu.pl/picturebooks>.

Phot. Olga Strycharczyk

In the academic year 2023/24, we are celebrating the 100th anniversary of the publication of the most famous Polish collection of Greek and Roman myths – *Mitologia* (*Mythology*, 1924) by Jan Parandowski. This book, along with Anna M. Komornicka *Historie nie z tej ziemi* (*Stories Not from This World*, 1987), inspired the students to write short stories. First published in Polish (*Mitologia tuż za rogiem*: <http://omc.obta.al.uw.edu.pl/opowiadania>) for Parandowski Day at our Faculty, now they are available in English, too: ***Mythology Just Around the Corner***. The students, supported by Marta and Milena Pszczolińska, worked hard on the English translation in order to be ready for *The Modern Argonauts* conference. They will present the book during this event. At this point, we wish to express our gratitude to the graphic artist Zbigniew Karaszewski who prepared the artistic layout of both language versions at Hermes' speed.

How to Get Here?

From Warsaw-Chopin Airport (Okęcie) to the City Centre and to the Hotel and the University

Airport Information for travellers +48 22 650 42 20.

You can take a train or a bus run by ZTM (the Public Transport Authority of Warsaw: <https://www.wtp.waw.pl/en/chopin-airport-waw/>).

The bus stop is located in front of the Terminal, very close to the “Arrivals” area. You can take bus No. 175. If you want to get to the city centre, get off at the stop DW. CENTRALNY or CENTRUM. If you want to get to the hotel, get off at the stop ORDYNACKA, then turn left in Warecka Street which leads to Plac (Square) Powstańców Warszawy. There, on the left, you will find our hotel GROMADA CENTRUM. If you want to go directly to the University, get off the bus at the stop UNIWERSYTET.

The railway station is located on the left of Terminal A (i.e., turn right when you leave the Terminal). At the railway station you can take the yellow-red train SKM (Rapid Urban Railway, <https://www.wtp.waw.pl/en/chopin-airport-waw/rail-connections/>) – on this train the ZTM tickets are valid. You should get off at the station WARSZAWA POWIŚLE. There you have to change to bus No. 111 (direction: ESPERANTO) and get off either at the stop ORDYNACKA – if you want to go to the hotel, or at the stop UNIWERSYTET – if you want to go straight to the University Campus.

We strongly advise you to use licensed taxi services offered at the Chopin Airport. Please note that the taxi fare table should be clearly displayed in the car’s window. The Warsaw Chopin Airport recommends the following taxi corporation: ELE TAXI (+48 22 811 11 11), see also here: <https://www.lotnisko-chopina.pl/en/taxi.html>. The taxi fare from this airport to the city centre is approx. 50 PLN.

From Modlin Airport to the Hotel and the University

Airport Information for travellers +48 22 315 18 80.

The most convenient low-budget option is one of three Modlin Buses, which starts at least once every hour from the parking in front of the airport – you can easily recognize the buses as they are the only ones recommended by the airport hence allowed to park near the entrance. Contbus buses (www.contbus.pl), white with the logo, and Flixbus buses (<https://global.flixbus.com/>), vivid green, go directly to Warsaw. You can buy the ticket online, at the airport, or directly on the bus, paying with cash (PLN/GBP/USD) or by debit card. The sooner you book, the cheaper the ticket is. Usually the price is less than 10€. Getting to Warsaw should take about 50–60 minutes.

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The Contbus costs 30 PLN (about 7 €) and can be paid with cash or credit card. As the Contbus website works mainly in Polish, you can purchase the ticket from the driver. The buses are spacious and there are usually spare tickets. The bus arrives to the stop localized near the bus stop DWORZEC CENTRALNY 01, in the very front of the Palace of Culture and Science, which is one of the most recognizable buildings in the centre of Warsaw. You can take bus No. 175. If you want to get to the hotel, get off at the stop ORDYNACKA, then turn left in Warecka Street which leads to Plac (Square) Powstańców Warszawy. There, on the left, you will find our hotel GROMADA CENTRUM. If you want to go directly to the University, get off the bus at the stop UNIWERSYTET.

The Flixbus website (<https://global.flixbus.com/>) works well in English and you can book your ticket from Modlin Airport to Warsaw easily, but the bus arrives to the stop which is not in the city center. All the buses stop at METRO MŁOCINY metro terminal. The travel needs to be continued with the metro – it is 8 stops, you should get off at the stop ŚWIĘTOKRZYSKA (https://www.wtp.waw.pl/wp-content/uploads/sites/2/2020/07/m_swietokrzyska.pdf) and walk along Świętokrzyska Street which leads to Plac (Square) Powstańców Warszawy. There, on the right, on the opposite frontage of the Square you will find our hotel GROMADA CENTRUM. While walking from METRO ŚWIĘTOKRZYSKA, Sezam and McDonalds should be at your right.

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Another convenient option from Modlin Airport to Warsaw is bus and train combined ticket (<https://lotniskowy.mazowieckie.com.pl/pl>). Special shuffle buses marked with the logo of Koleje Mazowieckie (Mazovia Rail) deliver passengers directly to the station PKP Modlin every 20–30 min. The schedule is well planned in accordance with train departures so the total travel time is about 50 min. The ticket is one for the trip and costs 22,40 PLN (about 5€). It can be purchased at the airport, mobile app, and sometimes also in the bus there is a rail employee selling the tickets. You need the ticket to **WARSZAWA CENTRALNA** Central Railway Station. You can pay with cash or credit card. The ticket is valid 75 min. (you have to write down the start hour on the ticket) so you can also use it in Warsaw buses, trams, and metro (in metro use the lift as it does not open the ticket gate).

Koleje Mazowieckie

In order to find the hotel, you have to leave the Palace behind your back, cross the huge Marszałkowska Street using the underpass, leave the underpass going up left and then turn right into Złota Street. Going straight all the time, at the third crossing on the left you will see Plac (Square) Powstańców Warszawy and the hotel's building. If you want to go straight to the University – please take the metro line M2 from the ŚWIĘTOKRZYSKA station, which you will find about 300 m on the left to the bus stop. You should get off at next stop: **NOWY ŚWIAT – UNIWERSYTET** and turn left into Nowy Świat Street which goes on into Krakowskie Przedmieście, where the University Campus is localized.

If you prefer to use taxi, please use only the service of two corporations recommended by the Modlin Airport: **OPTI TAXI** (+48 608 300 500) and **TAXI MODLIN** (+48 600 105 105). For more information please check here: <https://en.modlinairport.pl/page/taxi>.

From Warszawa Centralna (Warsaw Central Railway) Station to the Hotel and the University

Take the bus 175 which goes from the DWORZEC CENTRALNY 01 bus stop. After leaving the train you will find yourself in one of the underpasses which lead to the Station's main hall. Yet, if you want to take the bus, you should not follow the signboards directing to the main hall (in Polish: Hala Główna), but go in the other direction, in order to find Aleje Jerozolimskie Street and Hotel Marriott. The bus stop is situated right in front of the Hotel Marriott – you can have a look on the map here: <https://www.wtp.waw.pl/dworce-autobusowe-i-kolejowe/>, the spot marked as “BUS 01” is the 175 bus stop. If you want to get to the hotel GROMADA CENTRUM, get off at the stop ORDYNACKA, then turn left in Warecka Street which leads to Plac (Square) Powstańców Warszawy. There, on the left, you will find our hotel GROMADA CENTRUM. If you want to go directly to the University, simply get off the bus at the stop UNIWERSYTET.

If you prefer to use taxi, you should follow the directions on the signboards leading to the Station's main hall (in Polish: Hala Główna). In the front of the main hall you will see the taxi rank of the iTAXI corporation (+48 737 737 737). As this is the corporation officially chosen by the city to provide the taxi services from the Station, please use this one. We can also recommend SUPER TAXI (+48 22 578 98 00) – the corporation that we will use during the conference.

How to Buy a Bus/Train Ticket?

You can purchase a ticket at the newsagents' or at ZTM's ticket machines situated next to the bus stop or at the railway station. You can pay in cash or with credit/debit card – please note that the ticket machines accept only Polish złoty (1 PLN is approx. 0,25 USD or 0,23 Euro). A single 75 min. fare costs 4,40 PLN, but you can also buy a 24-hour or a 3-day ticket – for more information about fares and prices please consult here: <https://www.wtp.waw.pl/en/news/2022/03/22/public-transport-in-warsaw/>, here: <https://www.wtp.waw.pl/en/>, or here: <https://www.ztm.waw.pl/en/>. Attention! You are required to validate your ticket **immediately** after boarding the vehicle or – if you travel with the metro – **before** entering the platform.

Where to Stay?

The members of the Project's Research Team are staying at the HOTEL GROMADA CENTRUM, located at Plac (Square) Powstańców Warszawy 2, in the city centre, close to the University of Warsaw and to the Old Town. If you would also like to stay there, you can make your reservation at: <https://www.gromada.pl/en/about-the-hotel-page-155684>.

For other hotels and hostels in Warsaw please consult the Warsaw Tourist Information: <https://warsawtour.pl/en/warsaw-tourist-information/>.

Links

ERC Website <https://erc.europa.eu/>

ERC on *The Modern Argonauts* Project <https://erc.europa.eu/news-events/news/proof-concept-2023-highlighted-projects>

ERC on the *Our Mythical Childhood* Project <https://erc.europa.eu/projects-figures/stories/linking-classical-antiquity-and-modern-youth-culture>

UW on *The Modern Argonauts* Project <https://en.uw.edu.pl/first-erc-proof-of-concept-grant-in-polish-humanities/>

UW on the *Our Mythical Childhood* Project www.en.uw.edu.pl/11th-erc-grant/

UW's Clip on *The Modern Argonauts* Project <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8-WtyB-Ph7U>

UW's Clip on the *Our Mythical Childhood* Project www.youtube.com/watch?v=sWMX-5NuDRrU

Cordis Website *The Modern Argonauts* <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101122976>

Cordis Website *Our Mythical Childhood* http://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/205179_en.html

University of Warsaw www.en.uw.edu.pl

The Modern Argonauts: A Multicultural Educational Programme Preparing Young People for Contemporary Challenges through an Innovative Use of Classical Mythology (ERC Proof of Concept Grant, 2023–2025) <https://modernargonauts.al.uw.edu.pl/>

YouTube www.youtube.com/channel/UC6zvU9EXsI0gK5rSvgnQseQ

Facebook www.facebook.com/OurMythicalChildhood

X (former Twitter) www.twitter.com/OMChildhood

Instagram www.instagram.com/OMChildhood

Our Mythical Childhood Survey <http://www.omc.obta.al.uw.edu.pl/myth-survey>

Antipodean Odyssey <https://antipodeanodyssey.wordpress.com>

Autism and Classical Myth <http://myth-autism.blogspot.com>

Our Mythical Childhood Blog <https://ourmythicalchildhoodblog.wordpress.com/>

Panoply Vase Animation Project <http://www.panoply.org.uk>

Faculty of “Artes Liberales” UW <https://al.uw.edu.pl/en/>

OBTIMA <https://obtima.al.uw.edu.pl/>

Centre for Studies on the Classical Tradition (OBTA) www.obta.al.uw.edu.pl/en/index

Study Curricula <https://al.uw.edu.pl/rekrutacja/>

The Cluster: The Past for the Present <http://www.cluster.obta.al.uw.edu.pl/>
Department of Classical Philology and Italian Studies, University of Bologna <http://www.ficlit.unibo.it/it>

Department of History and Cultures, University of Bologna <http://www.disci.unibo.it/it>

Faculty of Education, University of Cambridge <https://www.educ.cam.ac.uk/>

Faculty of Humanities, University of Fribourg <https://www.unifr.ch/lettres/fr/>

Faculty of Languages and Literatures, Ludwig Maximilian University of Munich <http://www.fak13.lmu.de>

Alexander von Humboldt Foundation www.humboldt-foundation.de/web/home.html

“*Artes Liberales* Institute” Foundation www.ial.org.pl

Loeb Classical Library Foundation <https://lclf.harvard.edu/>

Our Mythical Childhood... The Classics and Children's Literature between East and West (Loeb Project, 2012–2013, archive website) www.omc.al.uw.edu.pl

Chasing Mythical Beasts... The Reception of Creatures from Graeco-Roman Mythology in Children's and Young Adults' Culture as a Transformation Marker (Humboldt Project, 2014–2017, archive website) www.mythicalbeasts.obta.al.uw.edu.pl

Our Mythical Childhood... The Reception of Classical Antiquity in Children's and Young Adults' Culture in Response to Regional and Global Challenges (ERC Consolidator Grant, 2016–2022) <http://omc.obta.al.uw.edu.pl/>

Mikołaj Rej XI High School in Warsaw www.rej.edu.pl

Mikołaj Rej XI Classical Profile www.facebook.com/jubileusz-klasycznynej/

“Strumienie” High School in Józefów www.strumienie.sternik.edu.pl

OBTA Studies in Classical Reception

Polish Literature for Children and Young Adults Inspired by Classical Antiquity: A Catalogue

eds. Katarzyna Marciniak, Elżbieta Olechowska, Joanna Kłos, Michał Kucharski

Warsaw 2013

www.al.uw.edu.pl/omc_catalogue

Tadeusz Zieliński, Queen of the Wind Maidens. Prologue

introduction Michał Mizera, translation from the Russian original Katarzyna Tomaszuk, English translation and textual notes Elżbieta Olechowska

Warsaw 2013

www.al.uw.edu.pl/zielinski_queen

Antiquity and We at the Centre for Studies on the Classical Tradition (OBTA)

ed. Katarzyna Marciniak

Warsaw 2013

www.al.uw.edu.pl/antiquity_and_we

Antyk i my w Ośrodku Badań nad Tradycją Antyczną (OBTA)

[Polish version of the above volume]

ed. Katarzyna Marciniak

Warszawa 2013

www.al.uw.edu.pl/antyk_i_my

Classical Antiquity on Communist Stage in Poland: Ancient Theatre as an Ideological Medium. A Critical Review

ed. Elżbieta Olechowska

Warsaw 2015

www.al.uw.edu.pl/theatre_communist

De amicitia. Transdisciplinary Studies on Friendship

eds. Katarzyna Marciniak and Elżbieta Olechowska

Warsaw 2016

www.al.uw.edu.pl/amicitia

Biographical Dictionary of Polish Women Classicists: 20th Century

ed. Elżbieta Olechowska

Warsaw 2018

<http://al.uw.edu.pl/book/biographical-dictionary-of-polish-women-classicists-20th-century/>

De viris mulieribusque claribus: Schools Endeavour Educational Materials

ed. Katarzyna Marciniak

Warsaw 2019

<https://library.open.org/handle/20.500.12657/58941>

Naturae cognoscere causas: Schools Endeavour Educational Materials

eds. Katarzyna Marciniak, Janusz Ryba, Barbara Strycharczyk, Olga Strycharczyk, and Anna Wojciechowska

Warsaw 2021

<https://library.oapen.org/handle/20.500.12657/58940>

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Barbara Strycharczyk and Anna Wojciechowska

Warszawa 2024 (forthcoming)

www.al.uw.edu.pl/adfontes

Fair winds and following seas!

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